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The seasonal forms of *Heraclides cresphontes* Cramer, 1777, and clarification of the status of *H. c. pennsylvanicus* F. H. Chermock & R. L. Chermock, 1945

Harry Pavulaan

606 Hunton Place NE

Leesburg, VA. 20176

intlepsurvey@gmail.com

ABSTRACT. The purpose of this paper is to visually illustrate the difference between the spring and summer forms of *Heraclides cresphontes* and to clarify the status of *Heraclides cresphontes pennsylvanicus* as a spring form. *H. c. pennsylvanicus* was described from a series of specimens of the spring brood, taken at State College, Pennsylvania. Shiraiwa, et al (2014) published a summary of the status of *pennsylvanicus*. Spring brood individuals from several locations are illustrated here and contrasted against summer individuals in those same areas.

Additional key words: Intrasubspecific, spring form, summer form.

INTRODUCTION

Pieter Cramer (1779) was the first to illustrate the familiar Giant Swallowtail - as ‘*Cresphontes*’ (**Fig. 1**). There was minimal descriptive text. The butterfly was described as being found “in New York and on the island of Jamaica, as well as in South Carolina”.

Fig. A. Cresphontes. Deze gestaarte Kapel of Pagie, heeft de grondkleur der vleugelen op de bovenzijde donkerbruin, daar de Mannetjes in tegendeel, (gelyk uit de afbeelding op de volgende Plaat Fig. B. te zien is,) dezelve zwart hebben. De blauwe vlakken aan beide zijden der ondervleugels bestaan uit glinsterende fiertjes. Zy behoort onder de Grieksche Ridder-Kapellen van den Heer *Linnaeus*, en word in *Noord-Amerika*, te *Nieuw-jork* en op het Eiland *Jamaika*, als mede in *Zuid-Carolina* gevonden.

D'Aubenton, Planch. enl. 69. La Festonnée.

Fig. A. Cresphontes. *Le fond du dessus des ailes de ce Papillon à queue ou Page est d'un brun-obscur, tandis que les Mâles au contraire (comme on peut le voir sur la Planche suivante, Fig. B.) l'ont noir. Les taches bleues des deux côtés des ailes inférieures sont composées d'atomes luisants. Il appartient aux Chevaliers Grecs de Mr. Linnæus & se trouve dans l'Amérique Septentrionale, à la Nouvelle-York & dans l'Isle de la Jamaïque, comme aussi dans la Caroline Méridionale.*

D'Aubenton, Planch. enl. 69. La Festonnée.

Fig. 1. Original description of *H. cresphontes* in Cramer (1779); Dutch on left, French on right.

Translation: "This tailed Chapel or Page, has the ground color of the wings on the upper side dark brown, as the males on the contrary, (as can be seen from the picture on the next Plate Fig. B.,) have the same black. The blue surfaces on both sides of the underwings consist of shimmering leaves. It belongs to the Greek Knightly Chapels of Mr. Linnaeus, and is found in North America, in New York and on the island of Jamaica, as well as in South Carolina."

Fig. 2. Illustration of *H. cresphontes* in Cramer (1779).

The illustrated specimen in Cramer (1779) depicts a summer form (**Fig. 2**) as evidenced by a broad irregular band of black on the ventral hindwing. It is unclear if the illustrated specimen came from a summer flight originating in New York or elsewhere. This (**Fig. 2**) is likely the illustrated specimen that the Chermocks referenced, for comparison to their *pennsylvanicus*. However, Shiraiwa, et al (2014) designated a neotype for *cresphontes*, represented by a spring form specimen from New York (**Fig. 3**).

Fig. 3. Neotype specimen of *H. cresphontes*. Photos courtesy © National Museum of Natural History, Washington, D.C.

The Chermocks (1945), in their original description of *H. c. pennsylvanicus*, provided the following: “The upper surface of this race is similar to typical *cresphontes*...The lower surface of this race is diagnostic, distinguishing this race from typical *cresphontes*. The yellow spots of the primaries are larger and more elongated than in the typical form. The marginal and submarginal rows of spots are separated by a very narrow black line which broadens between M_1 and the inner margin. The secondaries are uniformly yellow except for a transverse marginal row of the blue lunules bordered by a very narrow black line...” The authors concluded: “*Pennsylvanicus* is probably the northern race of *cresphontes*... After examining hundreds of specimens of this species from Florida and Georgia, west to Arizona and Mexico, we found no southern specimens comparable to the new race. However, examples from Ohio, Michigan, and Ontario exhibit the characters of *pennsylvanicus* and may be considered that race.” The holotype (**Fig. 5**) is deposited in the Carnegie Museum of Natural History. The labels of the types of both *H. cresphontes* and *pennsylvanicus* are shown here (**Fig. 4**). It is evident that the Chermocks did not examine adequate series of spring form *cresphontes* from Florida to note presence of the spring form.

Fig. 4. Type labels of *cresphontes* and *pennsylvanicus*.

Fig. 5. Holotype specimen of *H. c. pennsylvanicus*. Photo © by permission of the Carnegie Museum of Natural History.

HISTORICAL SYSTEMATIC TREATMENT OF *PENNSYLVANICUS* FOLLOWING ORIGINAL DESCRIPTION

Klots (1951) listed *Papilio cresphontes pennsylvanicus* at subspecific rank. The range was given as Transition Zone and Upper Austral Zone of Midwest. Klots stated: “Not a very well marked subspecies. Probably the species forms a gradual cline.”

Forbes (1960) noted: “var *pennsylvanica* Chermock & Chermock...it is the northern form, typical in Pennsylvania to Michigan...and invading New York, also as a spring form further south.”

dos Passos (1964) listed *Papilio cresphontes pennsylvanicus* at subspecific rank.

Emmel (in Howe, 1975) states under *Papilio cresphontes*: “The northern populations have been named *pennsylvanicus*...but this subspecies is only weakly differentiated.

Tyler (1975) listed *Papilio cresphontes pennsylvanicus* at subspecific rank, but comments: “Similar specimens are said to have been taken in Florida, in which case this would be a form rather than a subspecies.”

Miller & Brown (in Hodges, 1983) listed *Papilio cresphontes pennsylvanicus* at subspecific rank.

Subsequent authors did not consider *pennsylvanicus* at subspecific rank, thus the most recent treatment in Pelham (2023) reflects this.

DESCRIPTION OF THE SPRING AND SUMMER FORMS

An examination of specimens in the McGuire Center for Lepidoptera and Biodiversity, in the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, in the American Museum of Natural History, and in online images in www.iNaturalist.org and www.butterfliesandmoths.org confirmed the two distinct seasonal phenotypes, more pronounced in the north by flight period, and with considerable seasonal overlap in the deep south. The original description of *pennsylvanicus* is consistent with the spring brood of *H.*

crephontes range wide. Dorsally, *crephontes* varies little between spring and summer broods, though the males and females do show a small degree of dimorphism (**Fig. 6a and 6c**), with females displaying slightly reduced, slightly paler yellow patterns than the males.

The **spring form** (= *pennsylvanicus*) (**Figs. 6, 7 & 8**) is primarily identified by the narrow median band on the hindwing venter. The median band is black, containing a series of blue lunules within each wing cell. The large yellow ventral patches and markings on both sets of wings are greatly enlarged. Spring individuals display a reddish patch in the center of the ventral hindwing.

The **summer form** (**Figs. 9, 10 & 11**) is primarily identified by a broader median band on the hindwing venter. The median band is black, containing a series of enlarged blue lunules within each wing cell. The large yellow ventral patches and markings on both sets of wings are reduced in size, compared to the spring form. Summer individuals generally do not have the ventral reddish patch or it is much reduced.

The difference between broods is most pronounced in the north (**Fig. 12**), with little overlap in development of the seasonal features. Both wild-caught and ex-diapause lab-reared spring brood individuals in northern Virginia and Maryland display the spring form characters, whereas summer individuals that were wild-caught or lab-reared offspring of spring brood females will appear as the typical summer form.

In Florida, the spring phenotype is essentially identical to Pennsylvania spring forms, occurring statewide with records variably from December to April, as far south as Big Pine Key in the Florida Keys. The summer phenotype, however, is present statewide during all months. There is considerable overlap in the dates of the spring and summer phenotypes, which I consider variable depending on prevailing seasonal conditions. Warmer winter conditions will encourage production of summer phenotypes throughout the winter months. Intermediate specimens have been shown to occur in March and April.

In interior continental locations such as eastern Missouri, spring forms generally fly during the first (spring) brood, though along the Gulf Coastal Region to Texas, summer forms and intermediates are evident year-round. Summer forms are exclusively found during summer broods, range wide.

CONCLUSION

It is determined that the taxon described by F. Chermock & R. Chermock as *pennsylvanicus* represents the seasonal spring form of *H. crephontes* throughout the entire range of the species. It occurs infrequently as far south as the Florida Keys during winter months. The summer form occurs range wide during the summer months, and also infrequently with the spring form in Florida throughout the winter months.

Fig. 6. Spring brood, ex-Herndon, Fairfax Co., VA: (A) male dorsum, 5/25/1995; (B) male venter, (same data); (C) ♀ dorsum, ex-ova, em. 4/22/2004; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 7. Spring brood, ex-Gore, Frederick Co., VA: (A) male dorsum, ex-ova, em: 4/17/2012; (B) male venter, (same data); (C) ♀ dorsum, ex-ova, em. 12/19/2009; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 8. Spring brood: ex-Kingsley Plantation, Duval Co., FL: (A) male dorsum, 4/16/1983; (B) male venter (same data); ex-Hague, Alachua Co., FL: (C) ♀ dorsum, 3/16/1997; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 9. Summer brood, ex-Seneca, Montgomery Co., MD: (A) male dorsum, ex-ova, em: 7/9/1982; (B) male venter, (same data); (C) ♀ dorsum, ex-ova, em. 7/12/1982; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 10. Summer brood, ex-Gore, Frederick Co., VA: (A) male dorsum, ex-ova, em: 7/8/2006; (B) male venter, (same data); (C) ♀ dorsum, ex-ova, em. 7/8/2006; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 11. Summer brood, ex-Graham, Bradford Co., FL: (A) male dorsum, 8/20/2005; (B) male venter (same data); (C) ♀ dorsum, 8/25/2005; (D) ♀ venter, (same data).

Fig. 12. Comparison of typical spring (left) and typical summer (right) broods.

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